

Factors Affecting Parents' Acceptance of Distance E-Learning According of The Corona Pandemic

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Abstract

According of the corona pandemic, use of distance e-learning by universities emphasize the great role of parents in providing continuous facilities and guidance to facilitate their children to continue their academic courses. This research attempts to reveal the factors that influence parents' acceptance of university distance e-learning. Using the electronic questionnaire Instrument, the sample consisted of (239) parents. To test the hypothesis of the study, the researchers used the (SPSS AMOS) program, in addition to the Pearson correlation coefficient and simple regression, also calculated the model validity and confirmatory factor analysis evidence. The results of the study revealed three factors that affect parents' acceptance of university e-learning (financial ability, motivation, and Benefit). Emphasizing the importance of this research, it provides decision makers with the results of this research to improve the virtual learning environment and focuses on the importance of educating parents and their children to continue their education.

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Introduction

The corona pandemic has made countries all over the world completely dependent on distance education in educational institutions (schools and universities). In Jordan, the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research instructed universities to rely on distance education. The Jordanian government began at the end of March 2020 and will be supported by higher education and scientific research. The universities represented by the Ministry try to provide all the facilities to provide sufficient infrastructure for distance education (Mahasneh & Bani Taha, 2020; Murad, 2020).

The total reliance on distance education in Jordanian universities may be a qualitative leap, and this call has not been resorted to since the history of the Jordanian state, as distance education was antecedently utilized in half in universities and is not mentioned in some cases. The full dependence on distance education in universities has accelerated in creating selections by decision-makers concerning providing infrastructure for distance education, providing coaching for Faculty members, students, and technicians, buying, and developing e-learning systems, providing facilities for college students to like distance e-learning. On the extent of the Jordanian family, it is tried to produce the elements of distance e-learning for its kids, for example: (buying computers and sensible devices, subscribing to the net, providing AN applicable setting for his or her kids to immerse themselves in distance education, shopping for instructional aids) (Mahasneh, 2020).

Although decision-makers and families try to provide facilities for students and faculty members to use distance e-learning, there are gaps caused by the use of distance e-learning, including the difficulty of achieving educational outcomes related to practical courses in scientific disciplines such as medicine, engineering, agriculture and science due to the lack of manual practice, psychological and family pressure Introversion and lack of face-to-face communication between students, faculty members, and students among themselves).

Alsaeid (2020) affirmed that it is the duty of the family to work to achieve psychological balance among its members to ensure the success of electronic learning from distance, especially that students are associated with technology because of their like for games and when they turn to learning, they may hate it. Anxiety for the souls of her children.

Abd-Alqader (2020) indicates that parents have more time to integrate them into the educational process, and it is necessary to integrate them to achieve interaction and achieve the outputs of academic programs.

AL-ahmady (2020) emphasized that the family is required to provide all forms of support to their children and to surround them considering the distance e-learning, to contribute to the success of the educational process and to ensure the continuity of their children in the educational process.

Cornelius (2020) indicated five things that parents can do to support students in online learning, which are (building schedules and daily programs to follow up on distance learning, showing seriousness in teaching and perseverance in following up and motivating children, providing facilities for children by providing a suitable place and supplies. Basic equipment and materials to facilitate remote education, identify and train the platforms that children use, and continuous communication with teachers).

The success of distance education requires the integration of parents' opinions as one of the elements of the educational process with the perceptions of faculty and students in the educational process (Lontyeva, 2018). (Kvavadze&Basilaia, 2020) stresses that the use of distance education in teaching according of the Corona crisis is beneficial to the students' parents as it provided an interesting and loving environment for children due to the integration of children and their desire to use computers and phones compared to traditional education. The study of Al-Shayab (2020) confirmed that the use of distance education according to the Corona pandemic is an opportunity to integrate parents into the educational system as they are the element most closely linked with their students, as parents clarified their role in spreading a positive educational atmosphere at home, and their role in achieving psychological balance For children in light of the exacerbation of the Corona crisis, and parents expressed their children's love for education, which increased due to the fact that the educational materials contain audio and visual videos that increased their interaction with education, and that distance education opened new horizons for communication between teachers and students' parents, and made most Parents are able to organize their child's self-learning for various educational materials at home.

Parental participation is an important factor in students 'achievement in traditional education, and to support parents, they play a major role in the success of their children in the virtual learning environment, and distance education imposes on parents to assume new roles and responsibilities that are not familiar because their children participate in distance education, and many parents make great efforts. To understand the roles, they should play in learning their children via the Internet (Boulton, 2008; Murphy & Rodriguez-Manzanares, 2009).

Among the most prominent challenges that may affect parental involvement in the use of distance education are financial resources, lack of internet access, interest in using technology, low digital self-efficacy, (Hohlfeld et al., 2010; Hollingworth et al., 2011; Beckman et al. al., 2019; Povey et al., 2016).

The faculty members identified a set of effective educational tasks for parents in the light of distance education centered on organizing and managing students according to educational schedules, caring for relationships and interactions, monitoring, and motivating students, and guiding them as necessary (Hasler Waters & Leong, 2014).

The theoretical literature refers to the proposal of models for the acceptance of technology by a group of philosophers. The philosopher Daves proposed the model of technology acceptance (Tam), and it is one of the most important models explaining the factors affecting the acceptance of technology. Perceived and influenced by a set of factors which are user training, user perceptions, user attitudes affect intentions to use, user intentions determine the level of use (Abd-Alhaq&yaseen, 2008).

Families have an effective role in helping their children to indulge in distance e-learning, so that the outputs of academic programs are realized in light of distance e-learning, families must provide a set of facilities for their children, and from here this study came to reveal the factors affecting parents 'acceptance of e-learning from distance in universities.

After the researchers reviewed the theoretical literature and previous studies, they found studies related of the study, Al-anaze (2020) conducted a study entitled Parents' Attitudes towards the Role of the Distance Learning System in Teaching Arabic Language to Foreign Private Education Schools Students During the Corona Crisis in the State Kuwait, the researcher used the descriptive survey approach, and the study sample consisted of (273) parents, and the results of the study showed that the attitudes of parents towards the role of the distance learning system in teaching Arabic language for foreign private education school students during the Corona crisis were moderate. Parents face obstacles when using the distance education system with a moderate degree.

Lase, Eli Zaluchu, Orientiand Ndraha (2020) conducted a study aimed at identifying parents' perceptions of distance learning during the Corona pandemic in rural Indonesia. The researchers used the qualitative descriptive approach through the interview tool, and the results showed that parents do not have negative perceptions about distance education despite the effect of distance education on the economic burden of families, lack of time and the inability of parents to become teachers in the home, in addition to parents. Things worked to support the learning process for children at home to provide the Internet, help children master the materials, and participate in completing tasks or tests provided by the teacher. The study also indicates a decrease in the motivation to learn and the cognitive abilities of the children.

Zaccoletti, et al. (2020) conducted a study aimed at identifying parents' perceptions about the academic motivation of Italian and Portuguese students while banning the Coronavirus (a comparative study). The

researchers used the descriptive survey methodology, and the study sample consisted of (567) parents. the results of the study showed a decrease in student motivation in both Italy and Portugal, in addition to the decrease in student participation in extracurricular activities was linked to changes in academic motivation (students who had a lower decrease). In participating in extracurricular activities, they also had a lower reduction in motivation). Moreover, student age was significantly related to changes in motivation (for example, older students had less declines).

Hwang & Hariyanti (2020) conducted a study Investigating Students and Parents' Perceptions of the Importance of Contextual Learning at Home and the Mutual Impact on Technological and Educational Aspects of Learning in the Context of COVID-19 The results indicated the students' ease of using technological means, and the benefit greatly affected their positive attitude towards technological means and the intention to continue using distance education. It has been found that parents greatly influence their children's perceptions at home. In addition to parents 'ease of use and intent to use influenced students' positive attitude and intention to use in the educational aspect. Parents believed that the learning activity in real contexts was also beneficial and encouraged their children to do more participation. Parents worry that their children overuse mobile devices.

Al-Ajmi conducted (2021) a study aimed at identifying the psychological attitudes of parents towards digital learning according of the Corona pandemic, and the researcher followed the theoretical frameworks and previous studies. The results of the study showed that most parents do not agree with digital learning, especially among young children and people with special needs, for the following justifications: (Lack of self-skills in dealing with modern technology in distance learning on the part of students, parents and teachers, and the family's follow-up of the educational process from home. According to the Corona pandemic, the increase in family burdens, and the lack of support on the part of the government regarding the availability of internet networks and the tremendous pressure on the network, the lack of free internet, the lack of internet in deprived rural areas, the lack of computers for poor families and the lack of self-discipline on the part of students in the process. Educational organizations, the lack of interaction between the teacher and the student and the lack of advance preparation for this digital transformation on the part of educational organizations, students, teachers, and parents.

Baurzhan, Zulfiya, Zhuldyz & Fatima (2020) conducted a study aimed at assessing parents 'satisfaction with the quality of distance education in Kazakhstan during the Coronavirus, the study sample consisted of 31,300 parents who were surveyed, in addition to in-depth interviews with 65 of Parents. The results of the study showed that the age of the parent and the level of family income are positively related to the level of parents 'satisfaction with distance learning, while the number of children in the family is negatively related to the parents' satisfaction with the learning process. The study found a statistically significant association between parents 'satisfaction with the quality of education and their assessment of teachers' competencies, and the government's willingness to switch to the online / distance learning format.

Abuhammad(2020) conducted a study on barriers to distance learning during the outbreak of the Coronavirus: a qualitative review from the perspective of parents, the researcher used the descriptive and analytical approach. The study sample consisted of 248 participants, and the results of the study revealed four barriers facing parents in their endeavors to help their children in distance learning, which are: personal, technical, logistical, and financial barriers.

Abu Ubada (2021) conducted a study aimed at evaluating the experience of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in distance education from the point of view of parents. The researcher used the descriptive survey approach through the questionnaire tool. The study sample consisted of (310) parents, and the results of the study showed that the education experience from a distance in primary schools in Riyadh according of the Corona pandemic, it was a successful experience from the point of view of parents and students, with a very high and high rating.

It was found through previous studies that most of them focus on parents' attitudes towards distance education as a study (Al-anaze, 2020) and their perceptions as a study (Lase, Eli Zaluchu, Orienti, and Ndraha, 2020); (Zaccolletti, et al., 2020); (Hwang and Hariyanti, 2020) study that focused on identifying students and parents' perceptions about real education and the effect of ease of use and intention in shaping positive attitudes for students. There are studies that focused on the role of parents in education in the school as studies (Abu Ubada, 2021). The current study differs from previous studies to uncover the factors affecting parents 'acceptance of distance e-learning in universities.

2. Research Model

According of the Corona pandemic that led to the closure of universities and various educational institutions, universities and educational institutions as a result of these closures have to use distance e-learning to ensure students' right to education, and after reviewing previous literature (Masa'd, 2017; Salloum et al ., 2019) The factors that affect parents' acceptance of e-learning can be identified in four factors: (acceptance, financial ability, children's motivation, and benefits) as shown in Figure (1).

Figure (1) the proposed research model

3. Study problem and hypothesis

The Corona pandemic has caused countries to resort to total reliance on distance e-learning to preserve public health, and this has resulted in burdens on parents, including providing the necessary supplies for children to pursue their distance e-learning, in addition to the responsibility for follow-up and supervision. This is considered a surprising thing for parents because they were not fully prepared for this. Some of them are the employees and some of them do not have the ability to follow the education of their children. Hence, the study tried to uncover the factors affecting parents' acceptance of remote e-learning in universities.

H1: There is an effect of the physical ability of parents to accept distance e-learning in universities.

H2: There is an effect of children's motivation to accept their parents for e-learning in universities.

H3: There is an effect of benefits on parents' acceptance of e-learning in universities.

4. Study objectives and importance

The study aims to uncover the factors affecting parents' acceptance of distance e-learning in universities, an attempt to provide decision-makers in higher education with the results of this study to improve the quality of services provided through e-learning.

5. Methodology

The researchers used the correlational descriptive approach to uncover the factors affecting parents' acceptance of e-learning.

5.1 Participant

The study population consisted of parents who have children studying in universities and the study sample consisted of (238) guardians who were chosen by the available sample method, and the males formed 28%, and females 72%, and the percentage of educated people was more than high school 86%.

5.2 Instrument

The researchers structure an instrument for factors affecting parents' acceptance of e-learning (Factors Affecting Parents' Acceptance of E-Learning (FAPAE)), consisting of (19) paragraphs distributed into four dimensions of acceptance (6) paragraphs, financial ability (3) paragraphs, Motivation (3) paragraphs, benefits (7) paragraphs, for each paragraph there are five responses listed from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree, the total score ranges from 19-95.

5.3 Validity of Instrument

The initial version of the instrument was presented to a group of arbitrators (5), to ensure that the paragraphs belong to the dimensions of the tool, and the wording and clarity of the paragraphs, and the researchers made the proposed amendments, and the validity of the structure was also verified by calculating the correlation coefficient between each paragraph with the dimension that you developed, and ranged from Correlation coefficients between paragraphs and dimensions between (0.60-0.94) and all were a statistical function at $\alpha \leq 0.01$ as shown in Table (1).

Table 1. Correlation coefficients between the paragraphs and the dimensions to which they belong

N	Correlation with dimension	N	Correlation with dimension	N	Correlation with dimension
1.	0.83**	8.	0.94**	15.	0.77**
2.	0.81**	9.	0.93**	16.	0.81**

3.	0.74**	10.	0.60**	17.	0.79**
4.	0.72**	11.	0.73**	18.	0.77**
5.	0.85**	12.	0.73**	19.	0.80**
6.	0.82**	13.	0.79**		
7.	0.88**	14.	0.68**		

** $\alpha \leq 0.01$

The internal correlations coefficient between the dimensions was also calculated, and Table (2) shows that the correlation coefficients were all statistically significant at $\alpha \leq 0.01$.

Table 2. Matrix of internal correlations between device dimensions

	1	2	3	4
Acceptance	1			
Financial	**0.47	1		
Motivation	**0.43	**0.36	1	
Benefits	**0.73	**0.53	**0.50	1

** $0.01 \geq \alpha$

The results of the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) showed that the items of the tool were distributed on four dimensions as shown in Table (3).

Table 3. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

	Acceptance	Financial	Motivation	Benefits
FAPAE1	0.70			
FAPAE2	0.85			
FAPAE3	0.54			
FAPAE4	0.58			
FAPAE5	0.73			
FAPAE6	0.71			
FAPAE7		0.86		
FAPAE8		0.87		
FAPAE9		0.84		
FAPAE10			0.73	
FAPAE11			0.61	
FAPAE12			0.45	
FAPAE13				0.63
FAPAE14				0.57
FAPAE15				0.71
FAPAE16				0.73
FAPAE17				0.77
FAPAE18				0.72
FAPAE19				0.71

5.4 Stability of the instrument

The stability of internal consistency reached Table (4) Cronbach alpha for the instrument (0.92), Cronbach alpha values ranged between (0.73-0.89), which are acceptable values for the purposes of the current study.

Table 4. Stability of the dimensions of the tool and the tool as a whole

Dimension	Cronbach's α
Acceptance	0.88
Financial	0.91
Motivation	0.73
Benefits	0.89
Total Score	0.92

5.6 Examine the Model

The model was examined using Amos software version 23.0, where the results of Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) framework, tested the fit of the FAPAE. Robust maximum likelihood was used. A comparative fit index = 0.879 (CFI) ≥ 0.90 , Tucker-Lewis's index = 0.91 (TLI) close to .95, Incremental Fit Index = 0.93 (IFI) 0.90, root mean square error of approximation = 0.05 (RMSEA) between 0.05 to 0.08, the Weighted Root Mean Square Residual (WRMSR) = 0.020 value < 1.0 (Lin, et al., 2017).

Model fit Figure 2. shows the final study model that shows the efficiency of the model

Figure 2. the final model of the research

5.7 Statistical Treatment

To analyze the results of the study, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS VERSION 23.0) was used, where the descriptive statistics were used to calculate the characteristics of the sample, and the Pearson correlation coefficient was used to calculate the correlations between the paragraphs, the total score, and dimensions of the scale. An exploratory factor analysis of the tool was used, and the validity of the study model was confirmed by using the Amos program to calculate the evidence of validity of the model and the confirmatory factor analysis, and to examine the hypotheses of the study, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated, and this was verified using the simple regression coefficient.

6. Results and Discussed

Figure 2. shows that the correlation coefficients between the total number of factors affecting parents' acceptance of e-learning with each of the tool dimensions (acceptance, material ability, motivation, and benefits) came in succession (0.89, 0.69, 0.64, 0.92) and they were all significant. Statistically at the significance level $\alpha \leq 0.01$, which indicates the acceptance of the study hypotheses that indicate the existence of an effect for each of (material ability, motivation, and benefits) on parents' acceptance of distance e-learning.

H1: There is an effect of the physical ability of parents to accept electronic education remotely in universities.

H2: There is an effect of children's motivation to accept their parents for e-learning in universities.

H3: There is an effect of benefits on parents' acceptance of e-learning in universities.

The results of the simple regression analysis, Table (5), also showed that the P values were all statistically significant at $\alpha \leq 0.01$, and these results confirm acceptance of the study hypotheses.

Table 5. Simple regression analysis of the tool dimensions with the influencing factors

Hypothesis		Std. Beta	Std. Error	T-Value	P-Value	Decision
H1	Acceptance- Financial	0.47	0.055	8.275	0.000	supported
H2	Acceptance - Motivation	0.43	0.064	7.248	0.000	supported
H3	Acceptance - Benefits	0.73	0.048	16.434	0.000	supported

The researchers stress that the economic conditions of the family and the parents are important for parents' acceptance of remote e-learning. Parents who have financial savings can purchase all the technical and technological supplies for their children from (computers, smart devices, subscribing to the Internet, purchasing materials and assistive tools in education) as well. And the children's motivation for remote e-learning and the benefits that have been achieved to them greatly affect parents' acceptance of e-learning from distance, in addition to the degree to which parents devote themselves to following up and guiding their children during distance education. The results of this study are consistent with the results of the study (Lase & Eli Zaluchu, 2020; Orienti, Ndraha, Zaccoletti, et al., 2020).

According to the results of the study, the researchers suggest a set of proposals that play the role of parents in distance education, the most important of which are:

1- Holding virtual awareness lectures for parents by the bodies concerned with higher education on the following topics (the importance of distance education, the role of parents in distance education, the mechanism of using e-learning management systems and the applications used in that, how to provide a virtual learning environment that achieves the desired goals, how to use computers and smart devices and their applications in distance learning).

2. The necessity of reducing the tuition fees by the bodies concerned with higher education and related to the use of traditional facilities such as photography or related to the use of public facilities to support parents in purchasing the requirements of electronic education remotely.

3. Expanding the umbrella of Education for All by allowing parents and the local community who wish to attend electronic education lectures remotely.

4- The institutions concerned with higher education provide facilities for parents to purchase electronic media for e-learning at subsidized prices that enable them to purchase them.

5. Involving parents in making decisions related to remote e-learning to enhance their role in making it successful and achieving the goals of the academic programs.

6. Proposing free courses for parents about activating their role in the educational process and getting to know the faculty members and all the services provided.

7. Conclusions

The results of the study showed that there are three factors (physical ability, motivation, and benefits) that affect parents' acceptance of e-learning.

8. Recommendations

The researchers recommend decision-makers in higher education in various countries to take advantage of the results of the study to improve the virtual learning environment for students at home and to hold educational lectures for parents to clarify their roles in the light of electronic learning.

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Appendices (Instrument)

-Part One: Demographic Information:

a. Gender: Male Female

B. Academic degree: General Secondary University degree

-Part Two: Influencing Factors

Note: Put a sign (x) in front of the degree of satisfaction appropriate

N	Paragraphs	scaling
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		Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	disagree	Strongly disagree
.1	I believe that Distance e-learning is the safest option for universities considering the epidemiological condition that we are living through during the pandemic.					
.2	I encourage the continuation of Distance e-learning in universities.					
.3	I believe that Distance e-learning parallels education within educational institutions.					
.4	I feel that university students are excited to continue Distance e-learning.					
.5	Distance e-learning enables students to learn from anywhere, at any time.					
.6	Distance e-learning contributed to students receiving education at any time and from anywhere.					
.7	I have the financial ability to buy computer and smart devices to keep my children in Distance e-learning.					
.8	I have the financial ability to subscribe to the Internet packages that my children need to continue in Distance e-learning.					
.9	I have the financial ability to fulfill the requirements of Distance e-learning for my children.					
.10	The weakness of the e-learning used in universities contributed to the students' aversion to students' use of Distance e-learning.					
.11	Distance e-learning contributed to raising the cumulative rates of students					
.12	Distance e-learning contributed to the provision of funds allocated for students to buy books and go to universities or for housing.					
.13	Distance e-learning made students more enthusiastic about learning compared to teaching in a lecture hall.					
.14	Universities provide Internet packages, which contributed to the continuation of students' Distance e-learning.					
.15	Universities provide training programs for students on the mechanism of using e-learning systems					
.16	Contributed to Distance e-learning in the follow-up and guidance of my children.					
.17	Contributed to Distance e-learning, considering individual differences between students					
.18	Distance e-learning has contributed to giving students the freedom to express their opinions during the teaching and learning process					
.19	I feel that Distance e-learning enhanced the self-confidence of my children					

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